

Trends and Patterns of Ownership of Female enterprises in India: Analysis of Fifth and Sixth Economic Census

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ARTICLE DETAILS

Article History

Published Online: 09 March 2019

Keywords

Female Ownership, proprietary enterprises, Unorganised Sector, Female

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ABSTRACT

Ownership of enterprises is an important step for women empowerment and for inclusive growth. Raw data from fifth economic census (2005) and sixth economic census (2013) provided by Central Statistics Office (CSO) is used to comprehend the changes in ownership pattern of enterprises by gender with respect to working age population. The analysis of the ownership of enterprises at all India level, at regional level and at state level by gender is undertaken which reveals huge disparity. Between fifth and sixth economic census there is decline in male owned establishments in rural sector. Source of finance by gender are also analysed. The analysis is concluded by highlighting probable reasons for disparity along with suggestions to improve the conditions of women entrepreneurs and eradicate poverty.

1. Introduction

In India participation of women in workforce is at smaller scale than countries at same level of development. Women's participation in economic activities is desirable for equitable growth. Ratio of male to female population according to 2011 population census is 1.061 whereas when sixth economic census 2013 by CSO figures are analysed ratio of male owned enterprises to female owned enterprises is 5.475. These figures show the lack of female ownership in unorganised sector¹ as reported by sixth economic census 2013 by CSO.

Table 1. Aggregate Population and Enterprises: Gender wise

Gender	Population	Enterprises
Male	3.94E+08	44076692
Female	3.73E+08	8050819

Population figures according to 2011 population census

Enterprises figures according to Sixth Economic census conducted by CSO 2013

Source: Authors computation based on data of fifth economic census

An important factor has been highlighted by Ghani et al. (2013) that growth in employment and growth in enterprises in unorganised sector between 1994 to 2005 has been due to brisk growth in female owned enterprises. Mixed initial trends which emerge from Ghani et al. (2013) analysis is the unorganised sector which absorbs largest share of workers and which provides about 81.5 % of employment in manufacturing in 2005 has seen increase in participation of female owned enterprises. Although the scale of operation of female owned enterprises is small scale.

For both male and female the share of enterprises is higher in rural sector. Share of male population in rural and urban sector is 68.6 % and 31.4 % respectively whereas share of male enterprises in rural and urban sector are 58 % and 35 %

respectively. Similarly share of female population in rural and urban sector is 69 % and 31 % respectively but the share of female owned enterprises in rural and urban sector is respectively 65% and 35 % respectively. The larger share of women owned enterprises in rural sector indicate that the high share of enterprises in rural sector maybe due to pull effect for female entrepreneurs.

The existence of higher percentage of female ownership in rural sector shows presence of push effect is greater than pull effect Meera, (2017)². This statement implies that existence of female entrepreneurship is mainly for survival. This argument is further strengthened by figures provided by sixth economic census conducted by CSO which show that only 10% of workers are employed by female enterprises. 90% of workers are employed by male enterprises. Simultaneously considering male ownership in case of male enterprises sector wise 58% enterprises are in rural sector and 42 % in urban sector this shows push effect seems to be less dominant in case of male enterprises.

Ghani et al. (2013) have shown that not only India percentage share of entrepreneurship is lower than what is expected at this stage of development. But also, the male to female ratio in entrepreneurship is higher than its equals. This means that share of female entrepreneurs is lower than other developing countries at same stage development.

The Female labour force participation rate of women has declined in India since 2004. India is ranked 120th among 131 countries in female labour force participation rate Ranade, (2018).

In this chapter we discuss the trends and patterns of enterprises based on gender across fifth 2005 and sixth economic 2013 census across India, region wise and state wise. We highlight the differences between male owned

¹ Economic census records gender of only proprietary enterprises. Enterprises which are registered with some organisation, for such enterprises gender of owner has not been recorded.

² Pull Effect arises when demand is high and unemployment level is low.

enterprises and female owned enterprises. We demonstrate the sectors where male and female owned enterprises are concentrated. In the end we try to explain the ownership pattern of male and female owned enterprises through regression.

Gender diversity benchmark for Asia 2011 shows that India has lowest percentage of women being employed. India is a consistent worst performer in representation of women in workforce.

2. Data for Gender Based Analysis

We are using data provided by Central Statistical Organisation. Fifth and Sixth Economic census conducted in year 2005 and 2013 respectively. These enumerate gender of each proprietary enterprises. The information is provided on sector that is rural or urban where the enterprise operates. Total workers employed by each enterprise. Source of finance for enterprise. NIC code of the activity undertaken by the enterprise.

Along with Economic census data Population census data is used to calculate the disparity in ownership of enterprises based on gender.

We have analysed data of economic census for trends and patterns of for gender across fifth economic census and sixth economic census by caste and for sixth economic census we show pattern of ownership of gender by religion.

3. Theoretical Framework

Sociological theory claims that gender is a socially constructed phenomenon. It is not merely a biological phenomenon. It is constructed by culture. Research over time has highlighted the fact that there is gender gap in ownership of proprietary enterprises. Meunier et al. (2017) interpret this in terms of legal rights. Disparity in institutional framework³ both formal and informal. For entrepreneurship access to resources is important but also institutional framework is important. Formal and both informal institutions play a role in ownership pattern. Institutional framework also impacts access to resources.

Andriutaet al., (2013) have explained the fact women in developing countries face hinderances in formal labour market hence to escape unemployment and poverty they take up self-employment. There is a large body of research for developed countries proving the fact that the discrimination which is present in labour market is carried over to entrepreneurial activities too. The proprietary enterprises that are considered here are survivalist in nature and can be considered as a way out of poverty.

Birley,(1989) cited in Yadav et al. (2016) has highlighted the fact the changing role of women in society was the main reason that has impact on entrepreneurial activity taken by women. For example the author has taken the example if primary role of

women is assumed to be of a mother and wife. Hence women lacked network to start a business. They instead chose different activities from male entrepreneurs. As the role of the women in society changed the sectors in which women initiated an entrepreneurial activity too changed.Brush,(1992) cited in Yadav et al. (2016) has taken unified approach from psychology and sociology to explain gender related differences in entrepreneurship. She has highlighted the fact that women see their business differently from men. They see their businesses from perspective of association consisting of relationships. This is fundamentally different from how men see their businesses. But the review is based on society in 1980s US. The author has herself explained the fact that as the society changes so will the construct of female entrepreneurship.

Female entrepreneurship considering Institutional theory: A commonly accepted definition of institutions is that they are the formal and informal rules that organise social, political and economic relations North, (1990). They are the systems of 'established and prevalent social rules that structure social interactionsHodgson, (2006, p. 2).

4. How Institutional Framework Impacts Women Entrepreneurship

Fig 1. Source: Authors Computation based on North,1990

Fischer et al. discuss two theories social feminist theory and liberal feminist theory in context of gender and entrepreneurship. Social feminist theory suggests that due to men and women differ inherently due to process of socialization. The studies that have considered social feminist theory have found that there is no impact on business performance by inherent differences in gender. On the other hand Liberal feminist theory suggests that women are inherently different from men and are disadvantaged and discriminated due to orderly factors which deprive them of skills and education. These factors which deprive women of skills and education make their business performance worse than that of male owners.

A systematic study of business owners based of organisational skills, industry differences and attributes of owner by Kalleberg, et al. (1991) for 411 companies in US found that there was no such thing as women owned businesses are less successful and will not grow was found for these 411 companies.

In this context we analyse data of fifth and sixth economic census.

³ Institutional framework works through legal rights and through customs. Lack of formerly defined property rights are a hinderance for increasing female entrepreneurship. This could be solved by properly defined property rights. Informal institutional framework works through customs prevalent in a society.

5. Women owners at All India Level

Table 2. Gender wise enterprises and population for Fifth Economic Census

Gender	OAE Percentage	Establishment Percentage	Population Percentage
Male	89.37647	93.02962	51.69764
Female	10.62353	6.970379	48.30236

Source: Authors computation based on data of fifth economic census and 2001 population census

Disparity in ownership of Establishment is more than in ownership of Own account enterprise. This is a clear indication that women lack access to economic resources. 48% of women own only 7% of establishments. Women owners have 10% share in ownership of OAEs. Ownership of enterprises is in favour of male owners and as the scale of operation increases in terms of hired workers the ownership is strongly favourable for male owners.

Table 3. Gender wise and Sector wise enterprises and population for Fifth Economic Census

	OAE Rural	OAE Urban	Establishment Rural	Establishment Urban
Male	15180099	7913508	4571926	6358660
Percentage	87.74840788%	92.6748474%	89.81744094%	95.48493821%
Female	2119473	625495	518317	300673
Percentage	12.25159212%	7.325152597%	10.18255906%	4.515061794%
	17299572	8539003	5090243	6659333

Census Population data

	2001 Rural	2001 Urban
Male	218799759 51.138%	98187149 52.987%
Female	209054340 48.86112824%	87114254 47.01219343%
	427854099	1.85E+08

Source; Authors computation based on data of fifth economic census and 2001 population census

A trend from fifth economic census becomes clear. Women owned businesses have far more lower percentage share than their share in population both in rural and urban sector. The disparity is even more visible in urban sector. As Enterprises

hire workers the share of female owned enterprises decreases. Lower share of women owned enterprises in establishments show that women owned enterprises work on a small scale. The enterprises owned by women owners are survivalist in nature.

Table 4. Gender wise enterprises and population for sixth Economic Census

Gender	OAE Percentage	Establishment Percentage	Population Percentage
Male	83.19255	88.97828	5.13E+01
Female	16.80745	11.02172	48.69792

Source: Authors computation based on data of sixth economic census and 2011 population census

Disparity has decreased from fifth economic census to sixth economic census. But trend is same from fifth economic census. Still there is huge gap between ownership of

enterprises by women and their working age population. The gap between population share and enterprises share is greater in case of establishments.

Table 5. Gender wise enterprises and population for Sixth Economic Census

	OAE Rural	OAE Urban	Establishment Rural	Establishment Urban
Male	21632215	11517964	3860264	7066249
Percentage	82.609	84.31111	84.85486	91.40476
Female	4554053	2143301	688991	664474
Percentage	17.391	15.68889	15.14514	8.595237
	26186268	13661265	4549255	7730723

Population	2011 Rural	2011 Urban
Male	2.61E+08 51.12%	1.33E+08 51.78%
Female	2.49E+08 48.861128%	1.24E+08 47.01219%
	5.1E+08	2.58E+08

Authors computation based on data of Sixth economic census and 2011 population census data

The disparity still exists in sixth economic census but there has been redistribution of enterprises in favour of women to a

little extent. Women still own a smaller share of enterprises than their population. The lower share of enterprises owned by

women as compared to their share in population. The lower share of women enterprises which women own show that women have been deprived of assets. Age old restrictions on women to own assets has resulted in women owning lesser number of enterprises. When we break these results region wise for six regions of India the disparity becomes even more

clear. There are regions where disparity is less and regions where disparity is quiet low. There has been decrease in ownership of Establishments in rural sector and the decrease has been due to decrease in number of male owned establishments.

Table 6. Registration of Male of Proprietary enterprises and Female Proprietary enterprises

	Male	Female
Registered	17001265.36(94%)	1023463.07(6%)
Not Registered	31445257.98(73%)	11365907.87(27%)

*Authors computation based on data of NSS 73rd round July 2015 -June 2016
% of male and female out of total registered enterprises*

The proprietary enterprises which are considered here get the benefits and support only if they are registered. Fifth Economic Census does provide information about registration of enterprises but sixth economic census does not provide information about registration of enterprise. I have taken data

from NSS 73rd round to show that out of total registered proprietary enterprises in country 94% are owned by male and 6% by female owners. But out of unregistered enterprises 73% are male owned and 27% are female owned enterprises. Most of the female owned enterprises are unregistered.

6. Region wise Ownership by Gender

Table 7 Region wise Ownership by Gender Fifth Economic Census and 2001 population census

Region	Enterprise % Male	Enterprise Male	Population % Male	Population Male	Enterprise% Female	Enterprise Female	Population% Female	Population Female
North	97.20194	4626204	52.92473	41324299	2.798057	133170	47.07527	36756966
North Eastern	91.71206	1202192	51.97999	11931555	8.287936	108641	48.02001	11022576
Central	96.7572	5905768	52.22151	73917393	3.242804	197931	47.77849	67628468
Eastern	93.27039	6476620	51.70674	68292772	6.729615	467299	48.29326	63784338
West	89.24176	5432408	52.24592	48547504	10.75824	654886	47.75408	44373643
Southern	83.83247	10381001	50.12735	72973385	16.16753	2002031	49.87265	72602603

Source: Raw fifth Economic Census Data and Population Census data of 2001 population census

Male owners are overrepresented in ownership of proprietary enterprises. Female owners are under-represented in ownership of enterprises. The region with highest gender

equality is south where disparity is lowest. In northern region disparity between male and female ownership is highest.

Table 8. Region wise Ownership by Gender Sixth Economic Census and 2011 population census

Region	Enterprise Male%	Number of Male Enterprise	Population % Male	Population Male	Enterprise Female	Number of Female Enterprise	Population% Female	Population Female
North	90.17485	5874986	52.22028	52727015	9.825152	640119	47.77972	48243371
North Eastern	86.79979	2154718	51.07709	14733298	13.20021	327682	48.92291	14111919
Central	90.83793	8082148	51.82145	95408518	9.162066	815179	48.17855	88701584
Eastern	85.88067	7842028	51.50141	85262746	14.11933	1289279	48.49859	80291464
West	86.85615	8006980	51.99906	60176233	13.14385	1211688	48.00094	55549378
Southern	76.28318	12115832	49.76988	85868069	23.71682	3766872	50.23012	86662131

Source: Raw sixth Economic Census Data and Population Census data of 2011 population census

In sixth economic census there has been redistribution in favour of female owners. In both fifth and sixth economic census highest gender equality in terms of female ownership of enterprises exists in southern region. Central region has

highest gender disparity both in fifth and sixth economic census. The share of female owned enterprises is lowest in central region.

7. Premises of Enterprises by Gender

Table 9. Sixth Economic Census premises by Gender

Gender	Premises	Number of Enterprises	Percentage
Male	Commercial	18743064	42.52
Male	Residential cum Commercial	25333628	57.48
Female	Commercial	1857168	23.07
Female	Residential cum Commercial	6193651	76.93

Source: Raw Sixth Economic Census Data

Maximum number of enterprises for both male and female are run from residential cum commercial premises but for female this proportion is much higher. 77% of female owned enterprises are run from residential cum commercial this shows that most of the women owned enterprises are household based. High share of women owned enterprises being run from residential premises shows that most of the enterprises owned by female are survivalist in nature. This could also be an indication of cultural and social barrier that women face. We do

not have information about the age and marital status of women. The information could reveal as to why

An identifiable trend from fifth and sixth economic census highest number and percentage of female owned enterprises are in southern region. Eastern region has surpassed western region in percentage of female enterprises and number of female enterprises. While in fifth economic census central region had lowest number and percentage of female enterprises. In sixth Economic census it is central region.

Table 10. Activity Wise Ownership of Enterprises

Activity	Number of enterprises of male	Number of enterprises of female	Percentage Male	Percentage female
01 - Activities relating to agriculture other than crop prod	557244	52310	1.26	.65
02 - Livestock	8607401	2546345	19.53	31.63
03 - Forestry and Logging	442221	124475	1.00	1.55
04 - Fishing and aqua culture	443234	38637	1.01	.48
05 - Mining and quarrying	65030	7829	.15	.10
06 - Manufacturing	7345863	2399463	16.67	29.80
07 - Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply	27715	3323	.06	.04
08 - Water supply, sewerage, waste management and remediatio	118788	10144	.27	.13
09 - Construction	884478	47025	2.01	.58
10- Whole sale trade, retail trade & repair of motor vehicle	900100	30237	2.04	.38
11 - Whole sale trade (not covered in item-10 above)	807033	48648	1.83	.60
12 - Retail trade (not covered in item-10 above)	13619370	1432202	30.90	17.79
13 - Transportation and storage	2696511	124707	6.12	1.55
14 - Accommodation and Food service activities	1974088	223095	4.48	2.77
15 - Information & communication	252666	19853	.57	.25
16 - Financial and insurance activities	304102	76271	.69	.95
17 - Real estate activities	369152	46054	.84	.57
18 - Professional, scientific & technical activities	439953	30681	1.00	.38
19 - Administrative and support service activities	587370	45264	1.33	.56
20 - Education	510166	217474	1.16	2.70
21 - Human health & social work activities	594382	75395	1.35	.94
22 - Arts entertainment, sports & amusement and recreation	139039	18552	.32	.23
23 - Other service activities not else where classified	2390786	432835	5.42	5.38

Source: Raw Sixth Economic Census Data

Highest number of enterprises for both male and female are in livestock, manufacturing, retail trade and other services. Surprisingly female owners have highest percentage share in livestock and manufacturing. Retail trade does not involve repairing of motor vehicles and machinery. Male owners have

highest percentage in retail, livestock and manufacturing. In livestock most of the male and female enterprises are concentrated in activities related to collecting fur and wool.

Women Owners in Manufacturing

Gender differences in manufacturing from sixth economic census are quite clear. Out of 9745326 men manufacturing enterprises men own 75% of enterprises and women own 255 of enterprises. Women have highest percentage of enterprises in tobacco manufacturing.31.8%(764050 enterprises) which is double the number of male enterprises(353523 enterprises) in tobacco manufacturing. Male have highest number and percentage of enterprises in manufacturing in manufacturing of wearing apparel. Among top five manufacturing activities four activities are same for males and females. Manufacture of tobacco products, manufacture of grain mill products, starches and starch products, spinning weaving and finishing of textiles are common for both males and females. Whereas manufacture of other textiles is one of the main five activities of females , manufacture of furniture is main activity of male entrepreneurs. Ghani et al. 2013 have postulated that most of

the females have shifted from unpaid household work to opening a household based enterprise. We have found evidence for what Ghani et al. 2013 have postulated out of total proprietary enterprises 42% of male enterprises are commercial and 58% are residential cum commercial but only 23% of female enterprises are commercial. 58% of female enterprises are household based. In case of manufacturing 44% of male enterprises are commercial but only 14% of female enterprises are commercial. 86% of female enterprises are residential cum commercial in manufacturing. This is a huge difference not only between male and female enterprises in manufacturing. As noted earlier maximum share of women enterprises is in tobacco manufacturing which is mainly demand driven. If consumer demand shifts from tobacco manufacturing these small scale enterprises operating from household these enterprises would not sustain.

8. Distribution of Enterprises by Gender State wise

Table 11 OAE Distribution by Gender State Wise

		Fifth Economic Census				Sixth Economic Census			
		Male	Female	Percentage Male	Percentage Female	Male	Female	Percentage Male	Percentage Female
1	Jammu & Kashmir	198276	2569	98.7209	1.2791	288491	23012	92.61259	7.387409
2	Himachal Pradesh	167689	7765	95.5743	4.42566	249432	45229	84.6505	15.3495
3	Punjab	601601	14512	97.6446	2.35541	870249	83916	91.20529	8.794705
4	Chandigarh	44098	757	98.3123	1.68766	58365	4921	92.22419	7.775811
5	Uttarakhand	208394	8443	96.1063	3.89371	241923	26828	90.01753	9.982474
6	Haryana	531100	14834	97.2828	2.71718	704063	113224	86.14636	13.85364
7	Delhi	299697	9353	96.9736	3.02637	408845	50403	89.02488	10.97512
8	Rajasthan	1078850	42587	96.2025	3.79754	1722128	193234	89.91136	10.08864
9	Uttar Pradesh	2660297	63634	97.6639	2.33611	4452362	371730	92.2943	7.705699
10	Bihar	788174	12205	98.4751	1.5249	977362	90115	91.55813	8.441868
11	Sikkim	9016	1965	82.1055	17.8946	22744	4383	83.84267	16.15733
12	Arunachal Pradesh	11632	2228	83.925	16.075	13378	4438	75.08981	24.91019
13	Nagaland	14835	3090	82.7615	17.2385	26870	11840	69.41359	30.58641
14	Manipur	49659	28726	63.3527	36.6473	102636	84550	54.83102	45.16898
15	Mizoram	19754	12126	61.9636	38.0364	23226	12808	64.45579	35.54421
16	Tripura	130480	7593	94.5007	5.49927	164974	13168	92.60814	7.391856
17	Meghalaya	21540	13323	61.7847	38.2153	31263	21540	59.20686	40.79314
18	Assam	603397	17422	97.1937	2.80629	1284826	130338	90.7899	9.210099
19	West Bengal	2418328	225104	91.4844	8.5156	3705296	762247	82.93812	17.06188
20	Jharkhand	215386	6395	97.1165	2.88348	276054	19827	93.299	6.701005
21	Orissa	1083778	128159	89.4253	10.5747	1246274	223875	84.77195	15.22805
22	Chhattisgarh	315590	21942	93.4993	6.50072	465334	62328	88.18789	11.81211
23	Madhya Pradesh	1086920	53462	95.3119	4.68808	1166168	155898	88.208	11.792
24	Gujarat	1169407	345856	77.1752	22.8248	2259815	403569	84.84751	15.15249
25	Daman & Diu	4511	888	83.5525	16.4475	4533	566	88.89978	11.10022
26	D & N Haveli	3746	209	94.7156	5.28445	3693	352	91.2979	8.702101
27	Maharashtra	2227742	145572	93.8663	6.1337	3651604	580337	86.28674	13.71326

28	Andhra Pradesh	2237957	282175	88.8032	11.1968	3430141	1028658	76.92971	23.07029
29	Karnataka	1219900	291117	80.7337	19.2663	1455546	492506	74.71803	25.28197
30	Goa	30550	5317	85.1758	14.8242	46472	13539	77.43914	22.56086
31	Lakshadweep	1057	105	90.9639	9.03615	1347	329	80.36993	19.63007
32	Kerala	1371330	583728	70.1427	29.8573	1567840	863797	64.47673	35.52327
33	Tamil Nadu	2244477	385932	85.3281	14.6719	2190699	793646	73.40636	26.59364
34	Puducherry	19634	5368	78.5297	21.4703	24268	8192	74.76278	25.23722
35	A & N Island	4805	507	90.4556	9.54443	11958	2011	85.60384	14.39616

Source : Authors Calculation based on Fifth and Sixth Economic Census Data

Establishments Fifth and Sixth Economic Census :Gender wise

Table 12< -- Fifth Economic Census----->←----- Sixth Economic Census->

		Male	Female	Percentage Male	Percentage Female	Male	Female	Percentage Male	Percentage Female
1	Jammu & Kashmir	75473	1147	98.503	1.496998	88566	8280	91.45034	8.549656
2	Himachal Pradesh	39978	1383	96.65627	3.34373	50295	3944	92.72848	7.27152
3	Punjab	355844	7975	97.80798	2.192024	361836	27005	93.055	6.944998
4	Chandigarh	16571	456	97.3219	2.678099	15602	862	94.76433	5.235666
5	Uttrakhand	71251	2300	96.87292	3.127082	64205	4591	93.32665	6.673353
6	Haryana	222284	5425	97.61757	2.382427	229889	11300	95.31488	4.685122
7	Delhi	411436	10519	97.50708	2.49292	314924	20031	94.01979	5.980206
8	Rajasthan	583307	13888	97.67446	2.325539	512301	54758	90.34351	9.656491
9	Uttar Pradesh	980753	23552	97.6549	2.345104	1142568	110649	91.1708	8.829197
10	Bihar	335499	5702	98.32884	1.671156	327579	63495	83.76394	16.23606
11	Sikkim	4639	585	88.80168	11.19832	3954	921	81.10769	18.89231
12	Arunachal Pradesh	7024	1129	86.15234	13.84766	7117	1975	78.27761	21.72239
13	Nagaland	9141	1066	89.55619	10.44381	11352	1817	86.20245	13.79755
14	Manipur	12778	1645	88.59461	11.40539	25049	3736	87.02102	12.97898
15	Mizoram	4994	1424	77.8124	22.1876	7825	3020	72.15307	27.84693
16	Tripura	27592	1121	96.09585	3.904155	25854	1338	95.07944	4.920565
17	Meghalaya	20111	8507	70.27395	29.72605	23005	7990	74.22165	25.77835
18	Assam	255600	6691	97.44902	2.550983	380645	23820	94.11074	5.889261
19	West Bengal	1107646	60064	94.85626	5.143743	827644	69090	92.29537	7.704626
20	Jharkhand	203922	5897	97.18948	2.810518	202064	34905	85.27023	14.72977
21	Orissa	323887	23773	93.162	6.838003	279755	25725	91.57883	8.421173
22	Chhattisgarh	183943	10272	94.71102	5.288984	107625	15648	87.30622	12.69378
23	Madhya Pradesh	398620	14326	96.53078	3.469219	441963	67507	86.74956	13.25044
24	Gujarat	684352	97142	87.56971	12.43029	780898	125054	86.1964	13.8036
25	Daman & Diu	3947	177	95.70805	4.29195	3397	239	93.42684	6.573157
26	D & N Haveli	3738	81	97.87903	2.120974	4175	952	81.43164	18.56836
27	Maharashtra	1278814	56615	95.76054	4.239462	1228115	83963	93.60076	6.399238
28	Andhra Pradesh	988805	77087	92.76784	7.232159	1076710	177740	85.83124	14.16876
29	Karnataka	584607	50280	92.08048	7.91952	550467	53300	91.17209	8.827909
30	Goa	25601	3029	89.42019	10.57981	24278	3117	88.62201	11.37799
31	Lakshadweep	856	46	94.90022	5.099778	599	131	82.05479	17.94521
32	Kerala	558273	77091	87.86664	12.13336	487683	50120	90.6806	9.319398
33	Tamil Nadu	1126524	247153	82.00792	17.99208	1297002	293963	81.52298	18.47702

34	Puducherry	18017	1072	94.3842	5.6158	16690	1977	89.40912	10.59088
35	A & N Island	4759	370	92.78612	7.213882	4882	502	90.67608	9.323923

Source : Authors Calculation based on Fifth and Sixth Economic Census Data

Sikkim, Mizoram, Gujarat, Daman and Diu are the four states in country where OAE percentage of women owners have gone down. OAEs are survivalist in nature. Decrease in percentage share of women from fifth to sixth economic census shows that women trying to survive by running an OAE without hiring a worker have failed in more states than establishments which are run with a hired worker.

Meghalaya and Kerala are states in country where percentage of ownership of establishments of women have

decreased. But in all other states percentage of women owned establishments have increased.

Women in each and every state in India have much lower share in enterprises than their population share. Lakshadweep, Himachal Pradesh, Haryana, Tamil Nadu and Nagaland all have increase in women's ownership share of enterprises by more than 10% in a decade's time.

9. Source of Finance by Gender

Table 13 Fifth Economic Census: Financing by Gender

Source of Finance	Number of firms male	Number of firms female	Percentage of firms male	Percentage of firms female
No Finance	31587095.00	3356272	92.84	94.17
Assistance from government sources	511751.00	62508	1.50	1.75
Borrowing from financial institutions	1215661.00	80979	3.57	2.27
Borrowing from non financial institutions	544922.00	42541	1.60	1.19
Others	164764.00	21658	.48	.61

Source: Raw fifth Economic Census Data

Most of the firms depend on self-finance the percentage of self-finance is higher for female-owned enterprises than it is for male owned enterprises.

Table 14 Sixth Economic Census: Financing by Gender

Source of Finance	Number of firms male	Number of firms female	Percentage of firms male	Percentage of firms female
Self finance	38753517	6365447	87.92	79.07
Financial Assistance from Govt. sources	686267	270978	1.56	3.37
Borrowing from financial institutions	938605	86789	2.13	1.08
Borrowing from Non Institutions/Money Lenders	381195	67525	.86	.84
Loan from Self Help Group	136469	80660	.31	1.00
Donations/Transfers from Other agencies	3180639	1179420	7.22	14.65

Source: Raw Sixth Economic Census Data

A surprising feature comes out in sixth economic census where percentage of female firms having access to finance is greater than percentage of male firms having access to finance. Women entrepreneurship has got highest support via donations from other agencies. Government sources and financial institutions have provided loans to higher percentage of female enterprises than to male enterprises. This is in contradiction to what is assumed to be the case because women lack ownership rights they do not have access to loans but data of sixth economic census shows otherwise.

The picture has changed from fifth economic census where male owners had higher share of finance from institutions and agencies. Access to finance increased for both male and female from fifth to sixth economic census.

10. Probable reasons for High Disparity:

Women in Indian society do not have equal access to property. For starting a business lack of economic resources is hindrance. Primary role of women is assumed be that of a mother and a wife, so women are not encouraged to take risk and start an enterprise. They also lack the network which male entrepreneurs have. The data does not provide us with variables, but other studies have shown that women face discrimination not only in labour market but also in entrepreneurial activity. The enterprises which women run are mainly run from residential premises hence proving that these enterprises are survivalist in nature rather than entrepreneurial in nature.

11. Policy Implications

1. For enterprises to grow in unorganised sector they need benefits and subsidy there is need to reduce bureaucratic requirements. Especially low registration rate of women enterprises show that the procedure to register must be made easy.
2. Most of the women owned enterprises in sixth economic census are run from residential premises and because of social constructs women lack networks which men have access to hence women need support in access to new markets. It is not only skills which are required but also there must be demand for the product.

12. Conclusion

Women entrepreneurs must face cultural prejudices, social inequalities and child care burden. The current pattern which reveals high disparity in ownership of enterprises between male owners and female owners proves the fact.

There has been decrease in number of male owned establishments from fifth to sixth economic census in rural

sector. But there has been increase in number of women establishments in rural sector.

Gujarat one of the most industrialised state in country has registered decrease in percentage share of women OAE owners. Other than Gujarat Daman and Diu, Mizoram and Sikkim have registered a decrease in percentage share of women OAE owners, but Meghalaya and Kerala have registered a decrease in percentage share of women establishments from fifth to sixth economic census. Jharkhand, Lakshadweep, Bihar and D & N Haveli are states that have registered an increase of more than 10% in women owned establishments. The ownership share of women in enterprise share in country is much lower than their population share. There has been slight change in ownership share of women from fifth to sixth economic census. 77% of women owned enterprises are being run from residential cum commercial premises. Not only showing the lack of access to capital which women have to overcome but also they have to look after the family as well as perform on economic front to support the family.

References

1. Andruita, X., & Kartasova, J. (2013). FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP PATTERNS: A THEORETICAL COMPARATIVE STUDY. *BUSINESS SYSTEMS and ECONOMICS*.
2. Birley, S. (1989). Female entrepreneurs: Are they really different? *Journal of Small Business Management*, 32-37.
3. Brush, C. G. (1992). Research on women business owners: Past trends, a new perspective and future directions. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 5-30.
4. Ejaz Ghani, W. R. (2013). Local industrial structures and female entrepreneurship in India. *Journal of Economic Geograph*, 929-964.
5. Fischer, E. M. (1993). A theoretical overview and extension of research on sex, gender, and entrepreneurship. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 151-168.
6. Ghani, E., Kerr, W. R., & O'Connell, S. D. (2013, September). Female Business Ownership and Informal Sector Persistence. *Policy Research Working Paper*, pp. 1-33.
7. H.N, M. (2017). A Micro level study on motivational factors to Rural Entrepreneurship. *World Wide Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*, 254-258.
8. Hodgson, G. M. (2005). What Are Institutions? *JOURNAL OF ECONOMIC ISSUES*, 1-25.
9. Kalleberg, A. L. (1991). "Gender and Organizational Performance: Determinants of Small Business Survival and Success. *Academy of Management Journal* , 136-161.
10. Limited, C. B. (2011). *Gender Diversity Benchmark for Asia 2011*. Community Business Limited.
11. Meunier, F., Krylova, Y., & Ramalho, R. (2017). Women's Entrepreneurship : How to Measure the Gap between New Female and Male Entrepreneurs? *Policy Research Working Paper;No. 8242*.
12. North, D. (1990). *Institutions, Institutional Change and Economic Performance*. Cambridge: Cambridge university press.
13. Ranade, A. (2018, June 27). Reversing women's decline in the Indian labour force. *Livemint*.
14. Unni, V. Y. (2016). Women entrepreneurship: research review and future directions. *Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research*, 1-18.